

Clinical Features of Coronavirus Infection: An Updated Review

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Abstract

The coronavirus (CoV) family, particularly severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has garnered global attention due to the ongoing coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. This review article aims to provide an up-to-date overview of the clinical features associated with coronavirus infections. Here we explore the diverse manifestations of the disease, ranging from mild respiratory symptoms to severe respiratory distress and multi-organ dysfunction. Additionally, we discuss the latest advancements in our understanding of the clinical spectrum, risk factors, and long-term sequelae associated with COVID-19.

Keywords: Coronavirus, Clinical features, Risk factors, Immunocompromised, Public health.

1. Introduction

Coronaviruses, a family of enveloped RNA viruses, have long been recognized for their dynamic interplay between animal reservoirs and human hosts, showcasing a remarkable capacity for zoonotic transmission (Malik, 2020). The intricate genetic makeup and adaptability of coronaviruses have allowed them to traverse species boundaries, leading to sporadic outbreaks with varying degrees of clinical severity in humans. The emergence of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) and the subsequent global pandemic, known as coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), have brought renewed attention

to the significance of unravelling the intricacies of clinical manifestations associated with this viral family.

Coronaviruses, characterized by their crown-like appearance under electron microscopy, primarily infect the respiratory epithelium. However, the complexity of their interactions with host cells extends beyond the respiratory system, manifesting in a spectrum of clinical presentations. Beyond the immediate respiratory symptoms that often characterize the early stages of infection, the virus has demonstrated a propensity to affect multiple organ systems, giving rise to a wide array of clinical scenarios (Leao et al., 2022). The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, caused by SARS-CoV-2, serves as a stark reminder of the

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critical need to comprehend the diverse clinical features exhibited by individuals affected by coronaviruses (Asselah et al., 2021).

2. Clinical Manifestations of COVID-19

2.1 Respiratory Symptoms

The spectrum of respiratory symptoms associated with COVID-19 spans a wide range, encompassing mild manifestations such as cough and dyspnea to severe conditions, including acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). The respiratory system stands as the primary battleground for SARS-CoV-2, where the virus initiates its invasion by targeting the respiratory epithelium. The ensuing clinical manifestations reflect the intricate interplay between the virus and the host's respiratory architecture, offering valuable insights into the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying COVID-19 (Hasöksüz et al., 2020).

Mild respiratory symptoms often mark the initial stages of COVID-19, with individuals commonly presenting with a persistent dry cough and shortness of breath (dyspnea). These symptoms, while indicative of a respiratory infection, may be mild and self-limiting in a considerable portion of cases (Guan et al., 2020). However, a subset of patients progresses to more severe respiratory involvement, developing pneumonia characterized by bilateral infiltrates on chest imaging (Li et al., 2020). The severity of pneumonia can vary widely, with some cases remaining asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic, while others evolve into critical conditions necessitating intensive medical intervention.

In severe cases, COVID-19 can lead to the development of ARDS, a life-threatening condition characterized by widespread inflammation in the lungs, impaired gas exchange, and respiratory failure. ARDS represents a critical juncture in the clinical course of severe COVID-19, often requiring mechanical ventilation and intensive care unit (ICU) admission (Zhou et al., 2020). The

pathogenesis of ARDS in COVID-19 involves a dysregulated host immune response, leading to a cytokine storm and extensive lung damage. This hyperinflammatory state contributes to the severity of respiratory distress and underscores the importance of understanding the immune dynamics in COVID-19 progression (Carfi et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2020).

2.2 Extra-Respiratory Symptoms

In addition to its prominent respiratory impact, COVID-19 exhibits a multifaceted nature, affecting various organ systems and giving rise to a diverse array of extra-respiratory symptoms. The recognition of these manifestations is crucial for comprehensive clinical assessment and targeted therapeutic interventions.

2.2.1. Gastrointestinal Symptoms

COVID-19 has been implicated in a spectrum of gastrointestinal symptoms, ranging from mild nausea and diarrhea to more severe conditions such as vomiting and abdominal pain. Gastrointestinal involvement is thought to be mediated by the expression of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors in the gastrointestinal tract, providing an additional route for viral entry. The engagement of the gastrointestinal tract could arise from direct viral impact or an inflammatory immune response, potentially resulting in malabsorption, disruption of intestinal secretions, compromise of gut mucosal integrity, and activation of the enteric nervous system. (Wu et al., 2020; Kariyawasam et al., 2021; Freedberg, 2022).

2.2.2. Neurological Complications

Neurological manifestations associated with COVID-19 have been a subject of increasing scrutiny. Reports indicate a range of neurological symptoms, including anosmia (loss of smell), ageusia (loss of taste), headache, dizziness, and, in severe cases, encephalopathy and stroke (Mao et al., 2020). The neurotropic potential of SARS-CoV-2 and its ability to invade the central nervous system raise

concerns about the long-term neurological sequelae of COVID-19 and emphasize the need for neurologically informed clinical care (Carod-Artal, 2020).

2.2.3. Cardiovascular Involvement

COVID-19 is not limited to respiratory and neurological domains; evidence suggests a significant impact on the cardiovascular system as well. Myocardial injury, arrhythmias, and thromboembolic events have been reported in COVID-19 patients, contributing to the complexity of the disease (Guan et al., 2020, Salazar et al., 2020). The mechanisms underlying cardiovascular involvement may involve direct viral myocardial injury, systemic inflammation, and hypercoagulability. (Tajbakhsh et al., 2020; Long et al., 2022).

3. Risk Factors

Identifying the factors that contribute to the severity of COVID-19 is crucial for risk stratification, early intervention, and the optimization of healthcare resources. The multifactorial nature of severe outcomes in COVID-19 involves a complex interplay of demographic and clinical determinants.

3.1. Age

Age has consistently emerged as a pivotal determinant of COVID-19 severity. Advanced age is associated with an increased risk of developing severe disease and a higher likelihood of mortality. Older adults, especially those aged 65 and above, are more prone to experience severe respiratory distress, multi-organ failure, and complications such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) (Zhou et al., 2020, Zhang et al., 2023). The age-related decline in immune function, known as immunosenescence, may contribute to the heightened vulnerability observed in older populations (Chen et al., 2021).

3.2. Comorbidities

Several underlying health conditions significantly amplify the risk of severe COVID-

19 outcomes. Notably, individuals with pre-existing comorbidities, such as hypertension and diabetes, are at an increased risk of developing severe respiratory complications and experiencing adverse clinical outcomes (Yang et al., 2020).

These comorbid conditions are intricately linked to immune dysregulation, systemic inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction, creating a milieu conducive to the exacerbation of COVID-19 severity (Ejaz et al., 2020). Individuals with comorbidities should embrace preventive measures and necessitate meticulous management for their well-being.

3.3. Immunocompromised States

Immunocompromised individuals, including those with underlying immunodeficiencies or receiving immunosuppressive therapies, face a heightened risk of severe COVID-19 outcomes. Impaired immune responses compromise the ability to mount an effective defense against the virus, leading to uncontrolled viral replication and an increased likelihood of severe respiratory and systemic complications (Zhou et al., 2020).

Individuals with a history of malignancy and recipients of solid-organ transplants appear to face an elevated risk of experiencing severe manifestations of COVID-19, potentially leading to increased mortality. The intricate interplay between immunocompromised states and the novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, has been a subject of substantial investigation.

For patients with malignancies, the underlying cancer, and the effects of cancer treatments, such as chemotherapy or immunosuppressive therapies, may compromise the immune system's ability to mount a robust defense against viral infections, potentially rendering them more susceptible to severe outcomes in the context of COVID-19.

Solid-organ transplant recipients, on the other hand, often receive immunosuppressive medications to prevent organ rejection. While essential for maintaining the transplanted

organ's viability, these medications can weaken the immune response, creating a scenario where the individual may be more susceptible to severe illness if infected with SARS-CoV-2 (Fung and Babik, 2021).

3.4. Other Contributing Factors

In addition to the well-established risk factors of age, comorbidities, and immunocompromised states, a more nuanced understanding of the variability in COVID-19 severity has led researchers to explore additional contributing factors. Genetic predispositions, for instance, play a role in influencing an individual's response to viral infections.

Variations in certain genes may impact the immune system's ability to mount an effective defense against SARS-CoV-2 or regulate the inflammatory response, potentially contributing to differences in disease severity among diverse populations (Salzer et al., 2018).

Socioeconomic factors and disparities in healthcare access have also emerged as critical determinants of COVID-19 outcomes. Individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may face challenges such as limited access to healthcare resources, crowded living conditions, and employment in essential services that increase the risk of exposure to the virus. Moreover, disparities in healthcare access can affect the timely diagnosis and management of COVID-19, further exacerbating health inequalities.

Research findings have indicated that populations experiencing socioeconomic disadvantages may have a higher prevalence of comorbidities, which, in turn, contributes to increased vulnerability to severe COVID-19 outcomes.

Additionally, factors such as inadequate access to testing facilities and healthcare information may lead to delayed diagnosis and treatment, potentially influencing the overall disease trajectory. Thus, a comprehensive approach to addressing the impact of COVID-19 must

encompass a consideration of these social determinants to ensure equitable healthcare and minimize disparities in outcomes (Salzer et al., 2018; Huang et al., 2020; Williamson et al., 2020).

4. Long-Term Sequelae

The aftermath of COVID-19 extends beyond the acute phase, with a growing body of evidence highlighting the existence of persistent symptoms among a substantial proportion of survivors. Referred to as "long COVID" or post-acute sequelae of SARS-CoV-2 infection (PASC), this phenomenon underscores the necessity for in-depth exploration of the enduring health implications of the disease.

4.1. Fatigue

Fatigue stands out as a prevalent and persistent symptom reported by individuals recovering from COVID-19 (Ceban et al., 2021). Beyond the expected recovery period, many survivors experience profound and lingering fatigue, impacting daily functioning and quality of life. The mechanisms underpinning post-COVID fatigue are not fully understood, but they may involve a combination of lingering viral effects, immunological responses, and potential impacts on various organ systems (Carfi et al., 2020; Lechner-Scott et al., 2021; Nalbandian et al., 2021).

4.2. Dyspnea

Long-term respiratory complications, particularly dyspnea or shortness of breath, are frequently reported among individuals recovering from COVID-19. Even in cases where the initial respiratory symptoms were mild, persistent dyspnea can significantly impact post-recovery life.

The etiology of prolonged respiratory symptoms is multifaceted, encompassing residual lung damage, ongoing inflammation, and potential vascular complications (Carfi et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2020; Ochani et al., 2021).

4.3. Cognitive Impairment

Emerging evidence suggests that COVID-19 survivors may experience cognitive impairment as part of the long-term sequelae. Symptoms such as brain fog, difficulty concentrating, and memory issues have been reported, indicating potential neurological consequences of the viral infection. The exact mechanisms contributing to cognitive impairment are complex and may involve direct viral effects on the central nervous system or indirect consequences of the inflammatory response (Carfi et al., 2020; Varatharaj et al., 2020; Ceban et al., 2022).

4.4. Cardiovascular and Multi-Organ Involvement

Beyond the core symptoms of fatigue, dyspnea, and cognitive impairment, there is increasing recognition of cardiovascular complications and multi-organ involvement in long COVID. Persistent symptoms such as chest pain, palpitations, and evidence of ongoing inflammation have been reported, necessitating comprehensive follow-up and management strategies for affected individuals (Carfi et al., 2020; Nalbandian et al., 2021; Nie et al., 2021).

5. Conclusion

The evolving nature of the COVID-19 pandemic demands a dynamic and comprehensive approach to understanding the clinical features associated with coronavirus infections. The intricate interplay between the novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, and the human host presents a diverse clinical spectrum, ranging from mild respiratory symptoms to severe manifestations like acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). The identification of risk factors, such as age, comorbidities, and immunocompromised states, is crucial for risk stratification and targeted interventions. Furthermore, the emergence of persistent symptoms in a significant proportion of COVID-19 survivors, known as "long COVID," adds a layer of

complexity to post-recovery care, necessitating extended follow-up and ongoing research to unravel the underlying mechanisms.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the content presented in this manuscript.